

Data management plan (DMP)

Implementing Interactive Dynamic Volume Illumination with Refraction and Caustics

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	30/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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I General Information

I.1 Administrative information

PI:
FWF project number:
Internal Project ID:
DMP version: 01 30.11.2025
Contributors:
 Emanuele Grisenti, e12434686@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Researcher

I.2 Data management responsibilities and resources

Person responsible for data management and DMP: Emanuele Grisenti, e12434686@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62
Co-ordination of data management responsibilities across partners: Emanuele Grisenti, e12434686@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62
Resources costed in for RDM: There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

II Data Characteristics

II.1 Data description and collection or re-use of existing data

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data	description
P1	Rendered images	Images	PNG, JPEG	100 - 1000 MB	no	Images rendered by the implemented rendering algorithm.
P2	Application code	Source code	UTF8 text files	100 - 1000 MB	no	Source code for the final application

Reused datasets:

	dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data	description
	R1	Stanford Volume Data Archive	https://graphics.stanford.edu/data/voldata/	CC BY	no	Publicly available volume data repository containing MRI scans.
	R2	The Volume Library	http://volume.open-terrain.org/	Commercial use is prohibited and no warranty whatsoever is expressed.	no	Publicly available volume data repository from various sources including CT scans, MRIs and artificially generated data.
<p>Methods and software used for data generation and reuse</p> <p>The image data is generated with the purpose-built application compiled from the provided code, using the volumetric data specified above.</p>						
III Documentation and Data Quality						
III.1 Metadata and documentation	<p>Data organization, metadata, and documentation:</p> <p>The filenames will follow the projects naming convention as defined in the README and include a timestamp of creation. Version control is automated.</p> <p>As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at project level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.</p> <p>Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.</p> <p>As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.</p> <p>Documentation to reproduce the results will be provided in the README.</p>					
III.2 Data quality control	<p>Data quality control:</p> <p>The following data quality checks will be done: peer review of data.</p>					
IV Data Storage, Sharing, and Long-Term Preservation						

IV.1 Data storage and backup during the research process

Storage and backup facilities:

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Emanuele Grisenti (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

P1 (Rendered images), P2 (Application code), R1 (Stanford Volume Data Archive), R2 (The Volume Library) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute's administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

Data security and protection of sensitive data:

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
P2	writing	reading only	no access
R1	writing	reading only	no access
R2	writing	reading only	no access

IV.2 Data sharing and long-term preservation

Data publication and access conditions:

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	2025-08-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	MIT

	<p>Repository description:</p> <p>TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. https://researchdata.tuwien.at/</p> <p>Methods or software needed to access and use data: Compiling the code requires a C++ compiler and the open-source dependencies listed in the project README.</p> <p>Long-term preservation and deletion of data:</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 10%;">dataset ID</th> <th style="width: 20%;">location for long-term storage</th> <th style="width: 15%;">minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)</th> <th style="width: 55%;">foreseeable research uses and/or users</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>P1</td> <td>TU Wien Research Data</td> <td>10 years</td> <td rowspan="2">Members of the scientific community</td> </tr> <tr> <td>P2</td> <td>TU Wien Research Data</td> <td>10 years</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users	P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community	P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
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P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Members of the scientific community											
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years												

V Legal and Ethical Aspects

V.1 Legal aspects	<p>Personal data:</p> <p>At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.</p> <p>Intellectual property rights and rights of use:</p> <p>Information regarding rights and control of access to data has yet to be identified.</p>
V.2 Ethical aspects	<p>Ethical issues:</p> <p>No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.</p>